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[Abstract] What Drives Chinese Aid? Allocation, Selectivity, Rhetoric and Practice

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Disclaimer

This journal article is in the process of being published. Here is an abstract.

Abstract

China is the world's largest bilateral creditor to low- and middle-income countries, as an aid provider and foreign investor. The magnitude of these financial flows has attracted international attention, notably concerns with divergence from prevailing aid standards and recipient debt sustainability. This issue arises particularly on the basis that aid and loans are sometimes blurred when originated from China. Internally, the Chinese population was also critical of allocation of foreign aid given in challenging national macro-economic contexts.

This article tests the hypothesis of a normalization of Chinese outflows through an attempt to focus on aid and while considering a time span of over 20 years – from 2000 to 2021. The analysis of a number of determinants confirms that the countries that have increasingly attracted more FDIs and foreign aid in value offer more potential economic gains. In recent years, economic opportunity now weighs more than political strategy or recipient country needs compared to 2000-2008.

In parallel, the paper also tests the hypothesis that the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) has had to internally adapt its foreign aid policy supporting discourse and align words with deeds, gradually putting a lighter stress on pure (and sometimes condescending) benefactor's approach and a stronger on mutual benefits. Press clippings in Chinese language support the thesis based on an analysis of key words from about 40 articles and an automatized (GDEL) countercheck of recurrent vocabulary.

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This article tests the hypothesis of a normalization of Chinese outflows, both official and foreign direct investments (FDIs). The analysis of a number of determinants confirms that, in recent years, the countries that have increasingly attracted more FDIs and foreign aid in value offer more potential economic gains. Economic opportunity now weighs more than political strategy or recipient country needs.

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